

FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF α -Al₂O₃ NANOPARTICLES REINFORCED POLYAMIDE 6 COMPOSITE FILAMENTS

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Abstract

Polyamide 6 (PA 6) or Nylon 6 filaments reinforced with 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles are dry mixed and extruded by a single screw extrusion method. Tensile tests on single filaments have demonstrated that the average yield strength and Young's modulus of 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles reinforced PA 6 filaments are greatly improved in the range of 3–173% and 9–90% as compared to those of neat PA 6 filament, respectively. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) has been performed to compare thermal stability of as-fabricated composite filament with neat PA 6 filament. DMA results show that PA 6 composite filaments are more thermally stable in comparison with neat PA 6 filament. The structures of PA 6-matrix nanocomposite filaments are characterized by Small angle x-ray scattering (SAXS). SAXS results reveal that the radius of gyration and persistence length of PA 6 chains decrease with increasing the α -Al₂O₃ content. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) absorption spectra results reveal that α -Al₂O₃ enhances the bond strength of PA 6 polymer chains such as Al-CH, Al-O-H systematic bending, C-C stretching, Al-O and Al-C bonds. This confirms that the α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles can enhance the mechanical and thermal behavior of PA 6. In addition, the increment of radius of gyration and the persistence length of PA 6 polymer chains influence the mechanical and thermal properties of PA 6-matrix composite filaments.

1 Introduction

Recently, polymer nanocomposites have been received much attention due to their potential applications in high technology. Polyamide 6 or Nylon 6 is important polymer for many applications

including gears, fittings, and bearings in vehicles, monofilament for weed trimmers and fishing line [1-2]. However, better mechanical properties are needed for better performance and practical applications.

The mechanical properties of PA 6 nanocomposite can be enhanced by reinforced with high strong materials such as SiO₂ nanoparticles, Al₂O₃ nanoparticles, Carbon nanotubes (CNTs). Several studies have been reported on the mechanical properties of PA6 nanocomposite such as SiO₂-Nylon 6, Al₂O₃-Poly (ether ether ketone) [3], CNTs-Nylon 6 [4]. These suggest that nanomaterials can enhance the mechanical properties Nylon 6 matrix.

α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles have good physical properties, such as abrasion resistance, corrosion resistance, thermal stability, electrical insulation and high mechanical strength [5-6]. Therefore, α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles are potentially used as the reinforcing material in polymer.

In this work, the fabrication and characterization of α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles reinforced PA 6 filaments are investigated. The mechanical tests were performed using universal testing in tension mode and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). The crystalline and chemical bonds of the fabricated filaments were characterized by SAXS, and FTIR, respectively. The morphologies of α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 composite filaments were also studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to reveal the fractured surface and the dispersion of α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles throughout PA 6 matrix. The effect of α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles on the mechanical properties of PA 6 filaments is also discussed.

2 Preparation and Characterization

α - Al_2O_3 nanoparticles with average particle size of ~ 30 nm were synthesized by a simple chitosan polymer complex solution route at pH 3 and calcined in air at 1200°C for 2 h. 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α - Al_2O_3 nanoparticles powder were mixed with PA 6 pellets (Ultramid[®] B grade, BASF the chemical company). PA 6- matrix nanocomposite chips were extruded by the single screw extruder (short metering 4:1 Thermo Haake PolyDrive). Five thermostatically-controlled heating zones were used to melt the mixture at the temperature of 240, 250, 270, 250 and 220°C . The extruder process was continuous and PA 6- matrix nanocomposite filaments were allowed traveling through the die outlet and tension device for 0.1 of diameter filament. Tensile tests were conducted using tensile testing machine (Instron model 5566) on ASTM D 3822. The average values of yield strength, Young's modulus and percentage of elongation at break were reported. The fabricated samples of α - Al_2O_3 /PA 6 nanocomposite filaments were characterized by SAXS using the 2 m of sample to detector distance (BL 2.2, SLRI). Small Angle Scattering (SAS) data were analyzed by SAXSIT software. SAS data were used to determine the shape, size of polymer coiled chains i.e. radius of gyration and persistence length. FTIR spectra were measured using PerkinElmer instruments, spectrum one, USA in the range of 4000 - 450 cm^{-1} with absorption mode. The chemical bonds between α - Al_2O_3 nanoparticles and PA 6 polymer chains were indicated by specified FTIR absorption spectra. DMA test was performed by Mettler Toledo, DMA/SDTA861 based on ASTM D 4065. This test was intended to determine the storage modulus and loss tangent at tension mode under temperature range at -100 to 150°C with frequency of 1 Hz. Finally, SEM (JSM 5910 LV) was used to observe the tensile fractured surface of α - Al_2O_3 /PA 6 filaments.

3 Results and Discussion

The stress-strain responses of the 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α - Al_2O_3 /PA 6 and neat PA 6 filaments are shown in Fig. 1. It is seen from the stress-strain curve that the tensile properties of the 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α - Al_2O_3 /PA 6 filaments are better than that the neat PA 6 filament.

Fig. 1. The stress-strain curve of neat PA 6 and α - Al_2O_3 /PA 6 filaments.

The average yield strength and Young's modulus of 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α - Al_2O_3 /PA 6 filaments are greatly improved in the range of 3–173% and 9–90% as compared to those of neat PA 6 filament, respectively. On the other hand, the elongations at break of 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α - Al_2O_3 /PA 6 filaments decrease in the range of 12–18%, as compared to that of neat PA 6 filament. The addition of small amount of α - Al_2O_3 nanoparticles significantly affects the improvement in the mechanical properties of PA 6.

Table 1 Values of yield strength and Young's modulus.

Sample	Yield Strength (MPa)	Young's modulus (MPa)
Neat PA 6	27.30 \pm 9.13	282.77 \pm 123.51
0.5 wt.% α - Al_2O_3 /PA 6	28.24 \pm 4.93	297.75 \pm 5.02
1.0 wt.% α - Al_2O_3 /PA 6	74.53 \pm 19.87	730.50 \pm 104.91

It is noted that, there remains another question whether the 1.0 wt.% α - Al_2O_3 nanoparticle loading is the optimum. In an effort to answer that we have also tried to investigate the samples with higher content of α - Al_2O_3 (i.e., 2.0–3.0 wt.%). It has been observed that it is undesirable to extrude and draw PA 6 filaments with α - $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 > 1.0$ wt.% because of the presence of agglomerate nanoparticles, high viscosity of polymer and high torque of single screw.

In order to determine the development of various chemical bonds during polymerization, FITR

spectroscopy was performed. FTIR absorption spectra of PA 6 filament and α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles reinforced PA 6 filaments are shown in Fig. 2. Five peaks of chemical bonds have increased significantly, as indicated by the arrows with Al-CH at 1635 cm⁻¹, Al-O-H systematic bending mode at 998 cm⁻¹, C-C stretching at 973 cm⁻¹, Al-O at 899 cm⁻¹ and Al-C at 810 cm⁻¹ [7-8]. The FTIR results also reveal that α -Al₂O₃ enhances the bond strength of PA 6 polymer chains.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of neat PA 6 and α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments.

The dynamic mechanical properties of α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments are presented by the plots of storage modulus (E') and loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) as a function of temperature as shown in Figs. 4(a-b). The storage modulus (E') from DMA results of all samples decreases with increasing temperature as shown in Fig.3 (a). Glass transition region is accompanied by a dramatic decrease of E' in temperature breadth range at 0 – 50 °C. E' values in this region of 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments increase about 15.4 % and 25.8 %, respectively as compared to that of the neat PA 6 filament. The addition of small amount of α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles affects the absorbed thermal energy and tension force. At rubbery plateau, E' of all samples has the clear difference in values. E' values of 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments increase 31.2 % and 29.5 %, as compared to that of neat PA 6 filament. E' decreases when temperature is above 100 °C. Thus,

E' slightly changes and is higher in the rubbery plateau region. This indicates the cross-linked PA 6 polymer around the α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles. However, the cross-linked polymer is the network disruption at the α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles and the interphase creation leads to retarded dynamic [9-10].

Fig. 3(b) shows $\tan\delta$ of neat PA 6, 0.5, and 1.0 wt.% α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments as a function of temperature. $\tan\delta$ reveals the ratio of the energy lost to the energy stored during a loading cycle. This represents the energy relaxation phenomena of neat PA 6 and α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments. $\tan\delta$ exhibits three relaxations (α , β , and γ peaks) below the melting temperature. Firstly, at α peak, $\tan\delta$ values of 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments are 18.9 % higher than that of neat PA 6 filament. The α -relaxation is assigned as the glass transition temperature (T_g) of samples [11-12]. The T_g values of 0.5 and 1.0 wt % α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments are respectively 89.4 and 89.7 °C and increase about ~ 2.2 %, as compared to that of neat PA 6 filament.

Fig. 3. DMA results showing (a) storage modulus (E'), and (b) loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) for neat PA 6 and α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments.

It is clearly seen that the T_g increases with increasing the α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles content.

Secondly, β loss peak is assigned as the related process to some unspecified local non-cooperative mobility occurring in the in the sub- T_g temperature region [12-13]. T_β values of 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments are respectively 9.7 and 13.5 °C. This decrease is about ~ 42.2 % as compared to that of neat PA 6 filament. The β -relaxation temperature slightly shifts with increasing of α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles content. This suggests that α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles reduce the energy lost of polymer molecular chains motion at high temperature. Thirdly, γ - relaxation temperature (T_γ) values of 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments are respectively -75.1 and -68.1 °C. This increase is about ~3.8 % as compared to neat PA 6 filament. The loss tangent results indicate that α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles can induce the cross-linked PA 6 polymer chains, and the cross-linked polymer influences the storage modulus at high temperature. This confirms that α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles can enhance the tensile and thermal properties of PA 6.

It is seen that the improvements of mechanical properties and the changing thermal properties are strongly influenced by the interaction between α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles and PA 6 polymer chains. The interfacial interactions between α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles with PA 6 matrix are formed by four possible mechanisms. The first mechanism is the weak van der Waals bonding between the α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles and PA 6 polymer matrix, which is the main load transfer mechanism for α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles /polymer composites [14]. The second is the chemical bonds which are confirmed by FTIR absorption spectra [3]. The third is the mechanical interlocking between α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles and polymer matrix. In addition, the polymer molecular chains are crosslinked around the nano-reinforcing particles. This is one of mechanical interlocking interaction of polymer chains in polymer nanocomposites.

To determine the shape, size of polymer colied chains, SAXS experiments were performed. The three plots of SAS data represent the neat PA 6 and α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 nanocomposite filaments are shown in Figs. 4(a-c). Fig. 4(a) shows the scattered intensity as a function of the scattering vector q . The power-law slopes of two scattering regions are non-integer, We can infer the SAS data to reveal the rough surface of α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles [15-16]. There is no evidence of the sphere-like morphology. Fig. 4(b)

shows the Guinier plot. This is used to estimate the radius of gyration (R_g) which is taken from the slope of a line observed at low scattering vector in the range of $q \cdot R_g < 1$ [16]. R_g value of neat PA 6 filament is 9.45 ± 0.04 nm, whereas R_g values of 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments are 5.54 ± 0.03 nm and 5.60 ± 0.4 nm, respectively. This suggests that R_g decreases with increasing the α -Al₂O₃ loading.

Fig.4. SAXS plots of neat PA 6 and α - Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments (a) the Porod plot, (b) Guinier plot, and (c) Kratky plot.

In addition, the Kratky plot is the Iq^2 vs. q as shown in Fig. 4(c). A single peak near $0.556 - 0.565 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ presumably represents the scattering from the persistence length (L_p) of polymer coiled chains with nanoparticles homogeneously dispersed within polymer matrix [17]. L_p value of neat PA 6 filament is $16.38 \pm 0.04 \text{ nm}$, while L_p values of 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments are $9.60 \pm 0.03 \text{ nm}$ and $9.70 \pm 0.04 \text{ nm}$, respectively. This suggests that α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles slightly affect the PA 6 polymer coiled length [15]. The enhancement in the mechanical properties could be explained from the size of polymer, such as the radius of gyration and persistence length of coiled chains, which are changed due to inclusion. As the nanoparticle fillers are surrounded by the amorphous shell of polymer matrix, there will be a relative decrease in the nanoparticle diameter which effectively increases the nanoparticle volume fraction in the polymer nanocomposite, which in turn influences the mechanical and thermal properties [18-19].

Fig. 5 shows SEM images of the tensile fractured surface of neat PA 6 and α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments. The first region is the formation of a terraced slope surface which is called a V-notch, at the initial of the fracture process [3, 20]. Second is the formation of

a knot surface. It is seen that the aggregate α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles are coated by the PA 6 shell polymer. As the tensile stress on the single filament is increased, a segment of swell surface occurs as seen in SEM images. Third is the coarse hackle region which is featured by the hackly surface and the brittle behavior with tearing. This is different fracture surface, as compared to that of neat PA 6 filament. Figs. 5(d) and 5(f) show the fracture surfaces of the composite filaments with details of three regions in high magnification. The breaking load is supported by the first region which has considerably the largest area in slope surface. The large area and knot surface would require a large force to break. This indicates that in the second region, the knot surface can also occur due to the increases of the cross-link of polymer chains, the size of polymer coiled chains, and chemical bonding between the nanoparticles and polymer matrix, as seen in the results of DMA, SAXS and FTIR absorption spectra, respectively.

4 Conclusion

α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 composite filaments have been successfully fabricated by a single screw extrusion method. It is found from this study that the α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles can enhance the mechanical and thermal properties of PA 6; the interfacial bonds between reinforcements and PA 6 matrix play an important role in the mechanical and thermal properties of α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 nanocomposite filaments. These properties are influenced by α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles content. Moreover, the radius of gyration and the persistence length of PA 6 polymer chains are possibly important factors responsible for the enhancements of the mechanical and thermal properties. SEM observation on the tensile fractured surfaces of α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 composite filaments shows brittle behavior with swell surface. The improvements are related to (i) decrease of the R_g and L_p of PA 6 polymer coil length in nanocomposite filaments (ii) formation of the chemical bonds between α -Al₂O₃ nano-reinforcement, and (iii) changes in the fracture process induced by the infused α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles.

Fig. 5. SEM images of the tensile fractured surface of neat PA 6 and α -Al₂O₃/PA 6 filaments.

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